

SEMI-EMPERIC FEATURE DEPENDENCE EVALUATION METHOD TO INCREASE DIAGNOSIS ACCURACY OF CHRONIC DISEASES

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Abstract: In this paper, has been developed the neural network architecture and semi-empiric method were used to increase the accuracy of diagnosis of chronic diseases.

Key words: feature dependence, chronic diseases, neural network.

Chronic illness is a disease that lasts for more than a year. Today, one of three person of the world's population lives with some form of chronic disease. There are some chronic diseases which are often difficult to diagnose due to the fact that they are asymptomatic or have symptoms similar to other diseases. In such cases, AI algorithms can solve these problems, if appropriate dataset is available. For this reason, many machine learning methods and deep learning methods have been proposed today that help in early diagnosis of chronic diseases. The accuracy of these algorithms depends very much on the structure of the database. For example, data with a large number of features may have features that are irrelevant for classification. From this point of view, leaving only the most important features in the database can not only increase the classification accuracy of the algorithm, but also facilitate the application of this algorithm in real life.

For this reason, many feature selection methods have been developed today. We may mainly divide these methods into 4 groups: filter methods, wrapper methods, embedding methods and hybrid methods

But these methods have the following problems:

1. Some medical signs depend on other signs, and when the value of one change, the importance of the other changes in the classification of information. For example, while excess weight has any relationship with the risk of cardiovascular

diseases for middle-aged people, it is considered a significant risk factor for older people. Similarly, small changes in the heart ECG, which are considered normal for a healthy person, can be a risk factor for patients with diabetes. But AI methods cannot fully identify such relationships.

2. The issue of FI stability. Usually, the stability of the FI can change as more information is added or removed from the database. Only features that have not changed or changed very little are considered stable.

The method we would like to propose consists of the following steps:

1. Identification and selection of stable FIs
2. Determining the relationship between FI according medical practices,
3. Evaluation of the importance of the second feature for different intervals of strongly connected features. Training neural network (NN) for selected dataset.

In this research “Heart disease health indicators” dataset by Teboul, M. Limam, F. S. Rizqi, was used. We used the Decision tree method to determine the stable FI, because this method is considered a relatively stable method [1]. After that, the empirically determined values of the relationship between features were used for our research. Moreover, the empirical conclusions based on a dataset collected by Korean researchers from 9 278 433 people of different ages for 8.2 years [2] has been used, because the main reason for using such empirical inference is:

1. The existing feature dependence estimation methods cannot work with such a large volume of database;
2. Since such a large database is not open access, it is not possible to use it for training/testing AI algorithms.

Studies have shown a strong correlation between body mass (BMI) and age index, and this relationship has a U-shaped appearance (BMI changed in a U-shaped pattern with age). After that, the data of the elderly over the age of 70 was extracted and classified using NNs. The architecture of this neural network consisted of a total of 6 layers. The ReLu function was used as the activation function in the architecture. Also, a dropout layer with 20% following the sixth layer of the architecture was

used. Further Information about the parameters of the network layers is given in Table 1.

The classification accuracy of the network was 79.61%. In order to compare the effectiveness of this method, NN was trained with the same database (33344) but with data of all ages. Its accuracy reached 76.58%. It can be seen that the proposed approach allows to increase the accuracy of the network.

Table 1.

Parameters of the layers of the proposed neural network architecture

Layers' name	Number of neurons
Linear 1	21
Linear 2	32
Linear 3	64
Linear 4	128
Linear 5	64
Linear 6	32
Dropout	
Linear 7	2

In addition, since the empirically obtained results are several tens of times larger than the existing dataset, the correlation between features is calculated with high accuracy.

Summary

A semi-empiric method was used to determine the feature importance of the data in the dataset. Empirically obtained results on the basis of the very huge database are used. And this approach shows better performance than using results obtained automatically with smaller database. In addition, it has been shown that the existing methods of feature importance estimation cannot work well with such a large dataset.

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